

VIRAL DISEASES OF EQUINES

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ABSTRACT

Viral diseases in equine pose a continual threat so it is important to study to monitor their health, welfare, economic impact and the potential zoonotic risks of the diseases. Moreover, it is necessary to be aware about the several diseases so that new treatments and medications can be developed in research work. There are several viral diseases of equines such as Equine Encephalomyelitis, Equine Influenza, Equine Infectious Anaemia and many more. It is important to study the peculiar features of the diseases for their diagnosis. The necessary preventions against the diseases can include vector mitigation, maintaining hygiene among horses and their handlers, quarantine of infected animals and vaccination.

KEYWORDS: Viral diseases, equine, health, productivity, diagnosis, prevention.

INTRODUCTION

Viruses are acellular, microscopic entities composed of DNA or RNA that are either double stranded or single stranded and are enclosed within a protein coat called capsid which is composed of large number of units called as capsomeres. The nucleic acid and the capsid together is known as nucleocapsid which may be surrounded by envelope. They carry on their life cycle and produce disease with the help of host cell machinery (1). Viral diseases have always been a threat to animals because it interferes with normal activities and the productivity of animals. It is essential to study viral diseases in equines to check with equine health and welfare. Good Health of equines is of importance to us as well because they are used for transportation work, sports and recreational riding. Therefore, their productivity and well-being is of utmost importance to us. Moreover, it is important that we should be well aware of the zoonotic potential that any disease holds which might pose a risk of infection to human beings. There are several viral diseases that affects equines and their features, diagnosis and treatment is important.

EQUINE ENCEPHALOMYLELITIS

The aetiology of this disease is 'Alphavirus (Group A Arbovirus)' which belongs to Togaviridae. Three different strains are well known that is the 'Western strain', the 'Eastern strain' which is isolated from eastern part of United States and the 'Venezuelan strain' and is isolated from Venezuela. This arthropod borne disease may infect other vertebrates which including humans. Mosquitoes or other hematophagous insects may serve as vectors. Birds and rodents can also be involved in the spread of this disease. The bite of a carrier mosquito leads to entry of virus in the body, which then attacks langerhan cells and later attacks lymphoid tissue. Ultimately, the virus reaches blood causing viraemia leading to systemic infection (2).

It is a disease affecting central nervous system and it is manifested as loss of awareness, severe depression and flaccid paralysis that increases rapidly. Based on the clinical signs, the disease is also termed as Sleeping Sickness. No gross lesions are observed as such however microscopically